

Online Community Resilience: Governing Public Information Goods Under Attack

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Online communities steward a complex set of public information goods. These goods face a range of urgent threats, including strategic information pollution, governance capture; legitimacy attacks by external actors; and AI-driven disintermediation. How can online communities effectively defend information goods in the face of such attacks?

By evaluating existing community resilience and threat assessment strategies, we offer best practices for the design of community-level responses to these risks.

Public information goods face evolving threats as they mature.

As online communities creating public information goods grow, they face changing threats. Production-related problems like free-riding are salient early on when communities lack a critical mass of contributors. However, when they mature into high-quality information repositories—like widely-used free and open source software or Wikipedia—they attract adversaries motivated by ideological, political, or economic interests (Figure 1). In addition to engaging in outright manipulation, these adversaries may target the governance institutions, underlying resources, and public legitimacy of the commons itself. Several types of threats stand out:

Threat Type

- Free-riding
- Governance Capture
- Legitimacy attacks/commercial appropriation

Figure 1: The evolution of threats to public information goods. This conceptual model illustrates how four major threats to online information commons—free-riding, governance capture, legitimacy attacks, and commercial appropriation—fluctuate as communities mature.

Strategic degradation and pollution.

The introduction of false or misleading information, promotional content, vandalism, or low-quality contributions designed diminish the overall value of the public information good. This form of pollution can overwhelm quality control mechanisms and diminish user trust in the information good. *Examples: PR firms editing Wikipedia articles on behalf of clients; political editing on behalf of a state actor [1].*

Governance capture.

A takeover of the community's mechanisms for accountability and regulation by a small group of motivated actors. These actors may exploit procedural rules, covertly coordinate to dominate discussions about governance and decision-making, and place allies in positions of authority to bias content or enforcement in favor of their interests. *Examples: The takeover of Croatian Wikipedia by a small group of far-right nationalists [4].*

Commercial appropriation and disintermediation.

The large-scale extraction and re-provisioning of public information goods by commercial interests, often without attribution or compensation. This can suppress engagement with and contribution to the information resource and threaten its sustainability.

Examples: AI companies' harvesting of Wikipedia articles for training purposes and presentation of Wikipedia-derived content without attribution [2].

Legitimacy attacks.

Systematic efforts to undermine public confidence in the information good itself, often through meta-level criticisms of its processes, funding, or biases. Unlike direct content manipulation, legitimacy attacks target the perceived credibility and authority of the underlying information good as a whole, regardless of the quality of its content.

Examples: Elon Musk's call for Wikipedia to be defunded for alleged anti-conservative bias [5].

Community Recommendations: Defending Public Information Goods

Community resilience in the face of these threats to public information goods often requires tailored and context-specific interventions. Crafting an effective defense depends on the community, the challenges, and the nature of the attack(s) and attacker(s) involved. Our general guidance for community leaders emphasizes high-level strategic concerns and heuristics:

1. Identify the distinct public information good(s) that your community stewards. Is it factual knowledge, a deliberative space, a sense of trust, and/or a creative outlet? Clearly articulating what you are protecting will help identify defensive strategies and communicate the value of the good to both community members and the public.
2. Assess the maturity of the project, community governance institutions, and resources. Identifying the status of your community's resources, institutions, and vulnerabilities helps prioritize threats that require immediate attention versus long-term planning.
3. Distinguish among attacks against different elements of your broader *resource system*. Countermeasures that prevent content pollution may not defend against other threats. Recognizing which element of the resource system is under attack is crucial to designing an appropriate response.
4. Analyze adjacent governance systems, comparing successes vs. failures. Public information goods that are similar to one another (e.g., protecting similar goods, at similar stages in their life cycles, or with similar contributors)—may face comparable threats and benefit from similar defenses. Outcomes among similar communities may offer valuable lessons for designing successful defenses.
5. Consider tradeoffs and unintended consequences. Effective community defenses often come at a cost. Some are predictable, such as when enhanced rule enforcement causes decreases in new contributors. Others may be unexpected, as when account requirements to prevent low-quality contributions undermine activity among core contributors [3]. You cannot anticipate everything, but careful consideration and selecting defense interventions to precisely target root causes can help avoid negative surprises.

References:

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